

On the design of lignin reinforced acrylic acid/hyaluronic acid adhesive hydrogels with conductive PEDOT:HA nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogels are of great importance in biomedical engineering. They possess the ability to mimic bodily soft tissues, and this allows exciting possibilities for applications such as tissue engineering, drug delivery and wound healing, however much work remains on stability and mechanical robustness to allow for translation to clinical applications. The work herein describes the synthesis and analysis of a biocompatible, versatile hydrogel that has tailorable swelling, high stability when swollen and thermal stability. The synthesis methods used produce a hydrogel with high elasticity, good mechanical properties and rapid crosslinking whilst displaying biocompatibility, adhesion, and conductivity. It has been shown that cell viability in the samples is above 80 % in all cases, a Young's Modulus of up to 85 kPa and high swelling degrees were achieved. These materials show potential for use in numerous applications such as adhesive sensors, skin grafts and drug delivery systems.

1. Introduction

Hydrogel based materials are an ever-growing area, projected to reach a value of \$31.4 billion by 2027 [1]. This is due to its wide range of potential applications such as tissue engineering, drug delivery, wearable sensors, wound healing, etc. [2–6], making hydrogels a crucial material for biomedical engineering. Hydrogels consist of a 3D network that can absorb large amounts of water and swell to a large degree, they are versatile and suitable for biomedical applications as they are highly flexible, elastic, soft and can mimic biological tissues. The synthesis methods and materials used to produce hydrogels influence their final characteristics, they can range from porous and spongy to tough and highly stretchable depending on the steps used in synthesis. The properties of hydrogels such as swelling rate, degradability and stiffness can be tailored by modifying the polymer or crosslinker concentration, reaction conditions or their hydrophobic/hydrophilic ratios [7,8]. Despite their ability to closely resemble various biological tissues, hydrogels are still widely underutilised in practical applications, this is due to their generally low mechanical strength, low electrical conductivity and poor stability, thus limiting their feasibility in biological applications [9]. Due

to these shortcomings synthesising stronger, more stable hydrogels remains a crucial direction for research.

Natural polymers such as gelatin, collagen and hyaluronic acid make very suitable candidates for the synthesis of hydrogels for biological applications as they have high biocompatibility and are biodegradable. These commonly used biopolymers can be limited however, due to their poor mechanical characteristics and stability, which is their biggest challenge [9]. Synthetic polymers used for hydrogels such as polyethylene glycol (PEG), poly(vinyl) alcohol (PVA) and acrylic acid have good mechanical characteristics, good biocompatibility and high reproducibility but do not have cell attachment sites. For this reason, lately, hybrid or semi-synthetic hydrogels are preferred for practical applications as they combine the desired characteristics of both synthetic and natural biopolymers. They provide good biological activity and cell attachment with much needed mechanical characteristics and reproducibility.

Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a glycosaminoglycan that can be found naturally in the human body within the skin, connective tissues and synovial fluid joints [10]. Due to this, it has a high biocompatibility, viscoelastic properties and high-water retention which makes it highly

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suitable for biomedical applications [11]. However, it has poor residence time and can be subject to rapid degradation via oxidation or enzymes. In order to overcome this, HA can be crosslinked physically or chemically in order to form hydrogels which improves its stability and physicochemical properties while still maintaining its biocompatibility and biodegradability [5,12–16] and it can be combined with other materials that confer better mechanical strength. Lignin is a natural material, that provides mechanical support in the cell walls of plants and it has good biocompatibility, antimicrobial properties [17], mechanical characteristics and UV resistance. As well as its abundance naturally, it is also produced as a byproduct in the pulp and paper industry [18,19], but despite its abundance, it is considered under valorised. However, many researchers are investigating its valorisation into functional materials in biomedicine, controlled release, biosensors, electrodes, energy storage and as alternatives to PAN based carbon fibres [19–25]. When used as a filler in hydrogel applications, lignin has been found to improve adhesion and mechanical properties whilst maintaining biocompatibility [26,27]. Acrylic acid is an organic compound that, once crosslinked, can produce hydrogels with very high water absorbing capacity, also known as superabsorbent, meaning that they can absorb >400 times their weight in water [28]. Due to its inherent biocompatibility and biodegradability, it also has been widely used as a biological adhesive material, mucoadhesive drug delivery and surface coatings for biomedical devices [29–31]. Recent work completed by Fu et al. used both lignosulfonate and acrylic acid to form a highly stretchable, highly compressible and adhesive hydrogel material that highlights the improved characteristics that can be achieved by blending both materials to synthesise a highly conductive hydrogel, suitable for applications such as strain sensing and flexible electronics [32]. Additionally, Glingasorn et al. synthesised a bioinspired hydrogel combining acrylic acid and lignin, with the addition of hyaluronic acid in order to improve the water retention capacity and cell viability potential in the materials [33]. The combination of all three materials were found to improve the limitations of each individually and a synergistic result was achieved in the final biocompatible and biodegradable, adhesive hydrogel composite.

Conductivity is important in applications such as strain sensors, wearable devices, electro-stimulated drug delivery and electroactive cell stimulation [12,34–39]. However, most polymers commonly used in the formation of hydrogels have an inherently low conductivity. Conductivity can be conferred onto a material by the incorporation of a conducting polymer such as polyaniline (PANI), Polypyrrole (PPy) or poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene) into the hydrogel matrix [40,41]. Previous work by the current authors synthesised novel PEDOT:HA conducting polymer nanoparticles (NPs) that used hyaluronic acid as an alternative stabiliser to PSS and found the resulting nanoparticles to be stable, electrically conductive and biocompatible [42]. Conducting polymers can be combined with hydrogels to form stable conductive hydrogels for biomedicine [37,43]. PEDOT:HA NPs are a novel material and previously only work done by Wang et al. has characterised the incorporation of these NPs into a hydrogel scaffold application [44,45]. In their studies, Wang et al. incorporated PEDOT:HA NPs into a chitosan/gelatin matrix and found that the NPs not only improved mechanical and electrical characteristics but were also highly biocompatible, making them an attractive scaffold for nerve tissue regeneration and neural tissue engineering. These NPs have not previously been used in adhesive, conductive hydrogel applications and thus, this study aims to further the characterisation of these NPs into a novel hydrogel system, incorporating conductive PEDOT:HA nanoparticles into a lignin reinforced, acrylic acid/ hyaluronic acid hydrogel with good biocompatibility and bioactivity, while improving its mechanical properties, conductivity and stability.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Dulbecco's modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), Polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) (1.3 wt%), iron(III) p-toluenesulfonate hexahydrate (FeTos), hydrochloric acid, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) Acrylic Acid (Stabilised with hydroquinone), 3,4 Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT, 97 %), NN'-Bis(acryloyl)cystamine (98 %), Ammonium persulfate, trypsin-EDTA Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), 0.25 %, L-glutamine were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Ireland). Sodium Hyaluronic Acid (HA, 2 MDa) was purchased from Shanghai Easier Industrial Development Co. LTD. (Shanghai, China), Lignosulfonate and hydrogen peroxide 30 wt% was purchased from Analab (Ireland). Alamar Blue cell viability reagent was purchased from Invitrogen (Paisley, UK). NIH/3 T3 fibroblast cell line were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA).

2.2. Synthesis of PEDOT:TOS nanoparticles

For full details of nanoparticles were synthesis please see our previous work [42]. Briefly, HA is fully dissolved in 40 mL of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid (HCl). EDOT (0.2 mL) is mixed in the HCl solution for 10 mins. The mixture is cooled in an ice bath and sonicated using a Branson Sonifier 450 (1/2 in. tip, amplitude of 70 %, pulse of 90 %) for 10 min and a miniemulsion is formed. 1.277 g FeTos is dissolved in 10 mL of deionised (DI) water and stirred for 10 mins. A milky emulsion forms and is added dropwise to the reaction flask and polymerisation begins. Hydrogen peroxide is added after 1 h (0.05 mL) and the solution polymerises overnight. The produced Nanoparticles were purified via centrifugation three times, redispersing in DI water after each run. Once the solution becomes transparent, nanoparticles were redispersed in 40 mL of DI water and sonicated (Fig. 1).

2.3. Hydrogel synthesis

0.1 g of Hyaluronic acid (HA) is added to 20 mL of deionised water and the solution was stirred at 400 rpm overnight. Then, 0.25 mL of dispersed nanoparticles (as described in Section 2.2) were added to the HA solution and sonicated until full dispersion is attained. 0.2 g lignosulfonate (LIG), 3.6 mL of acrylic acid (AA) and varying amounts of NN'-Bis(acryloyl)cystamine (BACA) were added to the solution and stirred. Following this, 0.03 g of ammonium persulfate (APS) was added to the solution and stirred. The solution was then poured into a mould and placed in an oven for 2–4 h for 80 °C. Controls were also prepared containing no nanoparticles for comparison (Fig. 2). The compositions of each hydrogel synthesised can be seen in Table 1.

2.4. Rheological analysis

Rheology was carried out using a discovery hybrid rheometer (TA

Fig. 1. Synthesis of PEDOT:HA nanoparticles using oxidative miniemulsion.

Fig. 2. Synthesis process for hydrogels.

Table 1

Compositions of hydrogels denoted as: X_Y, where X is crosslinker amount (w/v %) and Y denotes if the sample contains nanoparticles (NP) or no nanoparticles (CON).

Sample name	NPs	Hyaluronic acid	Lignosulfonate	AA	BACA	APS
0.08_NP	0.25 mL	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.02 g	0.03 g
0.12_NP	0.25 mL	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.03 g	0.03 g
0.16_NP	0.25 mL	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.04 g	0.03 g
0.08_CON	–	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.02 g	0.03 g
0.12_CON	–	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.03 g	0.03 g
0.16_CON	–	0.1 g	0.2 g	3.6 g	0.04 g	0.03 g

Instruments, USA) and disposable 25 mm aluminium rheological plates were used. At a constant frequency of 1 Hz and 0.1 % amplitude, simple shear strain was given to the sample via torsional motion. The steps were as follows: initial temperature ramp to 80 °C at 5 °C/min and then constant temperature maintained at 80 °C for 2 h to observe the gelation of the samples.

2.5. FTIR

Spectra of the hydrogels were obtained using the Spectrum 100 FTIR (PerkinElmer, USA) for 4 scans in the range of 650–4000 cm⁻¹.

2.6. Morphological analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was used to visualise the morphology and distribution of the nanoparticles and hydrogels using a Hitachi SU70 SEM at 5 kV. Prior to imaging the hydrogels were frozen at 70 °C, freeze-dried for 2 days and then gold sputtered.

2.7. Swelling tests

Prior to swelling tests, the hydrogels were dried overnight in a vacuum oven. The samples were then initially weighed to get their dry weight (W_d) and placed in a vial of 10 mL of solvent for up to 48 h and weighed at specified intervals to get the wet weight of the samples (W_s). The hydrogels were dried with filter paper to remove loose water from the surface prior to weighing. The swelling degree of the samples was measured using the following formula:

$$\frac{W_s - W_d}{W_d} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_s is the swollen/wet weight of the hydrogel at specified intervals and W_d is the initial dried weight of the hydrogel.

Swelling tests were done in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) at a temperature of 37 °C and measurements were taken over the course of 48 h.

2.8. Diffusion analysis

The diffusion coefficient of solution within the gel structure was analysed using data recorded during swelling. Diffusion analysis was carried out under the assumption that the water uptake mechanism occurs in one dimension and the radial diffusion can be ignored compared to axial, as per Fick's law of diffusion. The diffusion coefficient of the samples was calculated using the following formula:

$$D = \frac{B^2 H^2 \pi}{16} \quad (2)$$

where B is the slope of M_t/M_∞ (M_t is the swelling after time t and M_∞ is swelling at equilibrium) versus √t, and H is the thickness of the hydrogel.

2.9. Thermal analysis

The water content and thermal degradation of the samples were analysed using a Perkin Elmer TGA 4000 in nitrogen. The samples were heated from 30 °C to 800 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min.

The glass transition temperature of the materials was determined using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a Perkin Elmer DSC 6. 6 ± 1 mg of sample was placed in an aluminium pan and heated from 50 to 200 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min to remove thermal history, cooled to 30 °C at 20 °C/min and reheated to 200 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. The T_g was determined from the second heating curve.

2.10. Mechanical analysis and adhesion

Tensile testing on the samples was carried out using a IMADA Force-Displacement Measurement unit. The samples were cut into dumbbell shapes and as per ISO527 Type 5B Tensile, the gauge length, width and thickness were 12, 2 and 1 mm, respectively. The elongation speed used was 10 mm/min and each sample was tested in triplicate, with the

average value shown. In order to plot the data, the stress (σ) and strain (ϵ) were calculated using the following equations:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon = \Delta l/l_0 \quad (4)$$

where F is the recorded load (N), A is the cross-sectional area of the specimen, Δl is the change in sample length and l_0 is the original gauge length.

The Young's modulus of the samples was calculated from the initial slope of the stress vs strain curve. The toughness was calculated by integrating the area underneath the stress-strain curve presented.

DMA analysis was carried out using a DMA Q800 (TA Instruments), in compression mode. The hydrogels were subjected to a multi frequency-strain sweep between 0.1 and 10 Hz at room temperature to determine the storage and loss moduli of the materials.

Hydrogel adhesiveness was evaluated by conducting a 90° peel test on porcine skin as shown in Fig. 8(a,b). Samples were cut into a rectangle of dimensions 15 mm × 50 mm × 1 mm (WHD). Tests were performed after 10 min adhesion to pig skin to ensure good contact. The samples were clamped and strained at a constant speed of 10 mm/min at room temperature. The adhesion strength was determined by the following equation:

$$\text{Adhesion Strength} = \frac{F_{\max}}{W}, \quad (5)$$

where (F_{\max}) is the maximum force and (W) is the width of the sample. Three measurements of each sample were obtained, and the average result is shown with \pm standard deviation. The hydrogels were also visually analysed to assess their adhesive characteristics by adhering them to glass, metal and plastic surfaces and picking them up using a spatula adhering to the other face of the hydrogel. An image is utilised to show the adhesion. An additional hydrogel labelled 0.16_CON_NOLIG (with the sample composition as 0.16_CON without any lignin) was tested in this analysis in order to compare to samples containing lignin.

2.11. Biological analysis

NIH-3 T3 fibroblast cells were cultured in DMEM with 10 % FBS, 1 % streptomycin-penicillin solution and 1 % L-glutamine at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere. The medium was replaced every 3 days until 80 % confluence was reached. Prior to cell seeding, the hydrogels were sterilised for 2 h using UV radiation, immersed in DMEM cell culture media in a 24-well plate for 72 h at 37 °C to reach equilibrium. Cells were seeded onto these pre-conditioned hydrogels at a density of 50,000 cells per well in a 24-well plate and these scaffolds were then supplemented with 1 mL of cell culture media and incubated overnight.

To carry out the evaluation of cell cytotoxicity, 10 % volume of Alamar Blue was added to each well and incubated for 4 h. Cell fluorescence was measured using SynergyMx (BioTek, UK) at a wavelength of 540/590 nm in 96-well plates. These readings were taken after 4 h, 24 h and 48 h after the addition of Alamar Blue. Cells incubated without the addition of hydrogels were also used as controls. In order to determine the statistical significance, one-way ANOVA was used, with a p -value of <0.05 considered to be statistically significant.

Following the same cell culture procedure as described above, NIH-3 T3 cells were stained with Calcein AM and propidium iodine in order to carry out live/dead fluorescence imaging on the ImageXpress Micro Spinning Disc Confocal High-Content Imaging System (Molecular Devices). This allows the visualisation of cell attachment and viability on the hydrogels. Images were processed and analysed using Fuji software.

2.12. Conductivity analysis

Dielectric measurements in the frequency range from 5×10^{-2} to 3×10^6 Hz were performed using a Novocontrol Broadband Dielectric Spectrometer (Hundsagen, Germany) consisting of an Alpha Analyzer. The measurements were performed in N₂ atmosphere at 37 °C using the temperature control system of a Novocontrol Quatro cryosystem, with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C during each sweep in frequency. Disc shaped samples of about 3–4 mm thickness and 10 mm diameter were used for analysis. The experimental uncertainty was <5 % in all cases. Measurements were made both with hydrated and dried samples. Measurements were carried out with an excitation voltage of 1 V. Five repeat measurements were carried out for each composition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydrogel synthesis

Rheometry measurements were conducted to determine curing kinetics. As shown in Fig. 3(a) it is evident that gelation begins to occur at around 50 to 60° Celsius. Gels with higher crosslinker content i.e. 0.16_CON and 0.16_NP cure faster at lower temperatures. It is also evident that the addition of nanoparticles influences crosslinking rates with control samples exhibiting lower overall viscosity than their NP counterparts after 2 h, except for in the 0.08 samples in which the addition of nanoparticles decreased its viscosity and a flat profile can be seen. This is likely due to the addition of nanoparticles preventing efficient crosslinking in these samples, and thus poor gelation is indicated by low viscosity. The addition of nanoparticles to the 0.16 sample greatly increases its viscosity, this is likely due to the 0.16_CON sample crosslinking very quickly, gelling and subsequent slippage occurs between the plates. The addition of nanoparticles to the 0.16 samples, slows the crosslinking, and the curve obtained indicates that it follows a similar trend to the other samples. The addition of nanoparticles causes the hydrogels to continue to react for longer periods of time possibly due to NP inhibition of reaction times. With the nanoparticles acting as a filler in the AA:HA matrix, this effects the crosslinking efficiency between chains, which is common for highly crosslinked hydrogels loaded with these types of NPs [39]. As seen in Fig. 3(b) the viscosity of samples 0.08_CON, 0.12_CON and 0.12_NP have all plateaued after 2.5 h with differing levels of viscosity. In general, when scaled up, the most consistently cured hydrogels were the 0.12_CON and the 0.12_NP samples and the crosslinking times of the 0.08 and 0.16 samples were found to vary depending on the desired thickness of samples and nanoparticle dispersion within the gels.

3.2. Structural analysis

Structural analysis of the hydrogels were performed using FTIR and results are shown in Fig. 4. A broad absorption band can be seen in the range 3600 and 3100 cm⁻¹ indicating -OH stretching and successful crosslinking via ester linkage, this is further confirmed by the formation of a peak at 1716 cm⁻¹. The peak at 2931 cm⁻¹ is attributed to an OH peak and may further indicate the formation of hydrogen bonds between the PAA chains and. The peak at 1633 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of HA and the peak at 1040 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of lignin in the hydrogel, suggesting that they have both been incorporated successfully. In addition, the characteristic PAA peak is observed at 1448 cm⁻¹ and this is attributed to C–N vibration [46,47] which indicates successful polymerising of acrylic acid. These results indicate that acrylic acid was successfully polymerized into polyacrylic acid and the PAA hydrogel was formed.

SEM analysis was also employed for morphological analysis of the hydrogels. Fig. 5 shows the cross section of the final AA/HA/LIG/PEDOT:HA hydrogels following lyophilisation. As shown in Fig. 5(A), following lyophilisation, the hydrogels formed an interconnected porous

Fig. 3. Complex viscosity of hydrogels (a) vs temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) on an initial temperature ramp to 80°C and (b) vs time (s) over 2.5 h, held at 80°C .

Fig. 4. FTIR Spectra of 0.08_LN2_NP, 0.12_LN2_NP and 0.16_LN2_NP hydrogel samples.

structure due to the sublimation of frozen water during freeze-drying. The 0.12_NP and 0.12_CON samples show the most regular, interconnected porosity, with the 0.08_NP and 0.16_NP samples displaying a much larger porosity and irregular pore network. Fig. 5(B) shows a more magnified view of the structure of the material within the pore network. Previous characterisation done by the authors has found that PEDOT:HA nanoparticles tend to agglomerate [42] and due to this tendency it is difficult to visualise individual nanoparticles within the hydrogel network. However, in Fig. 5 clusters of nanoparticles can be seen on the surface of the struts and embedded into the hydrogels and nanoparticles had good distribution throughout the scaffolds. In the 0.12_CON sample, the surface within the struts is seen to be completely smooth as there are no nanoparticles present in this scaffold, further supporting the successful distribution of nanoparticles into the 0.08_NP, 0.12_NP and 0.16_NP samples.

3.3. Hydrogel swelling

Swelling of the hydrogels was measured over the course of two days in PBS. Fig. 6 shows, all hydrogels exhibit high swelling degrees. In the control samples, a distinct correlation can be seen between crosslinking degree and swelling ratio, with an increase in crosslinking density causing a decrease in swelling degree as expected. In the samples containing 1 % nanoparticles however, there is not as large of a difference

between swelling degrees with swelling ranging from 8074.7 ± 589.7 in 0.08_NP to 9714.4 ± 680.5 in 0.16_NP samples, this indicates that the addition of nanoparticles helps to control swelling. The 0.08_CON sample begins to degrade at 24 h due to the hydrogel overswelling and disintegration of the gel, the high swelling degree of these samples is due to low crosslink density and this leads to poor stability. The addition of NPs to this sample lowered the swelling degree due to increased crosslinking density in these samples [5] and tended to plateau after 12 h. In the 0.16 samples, the addition of nanoparticles increased its swelling degree, indicating a disruption to the crosslinking efficiency in these samples. With the nanoparticles acting as a filler in the AA:HA matrix, this effects the crosslinking efficiency between chains, which is common for highly crosslinked hydrogels loaded with these types of NPs [39]. In general, the hydrogels in this study, swell to a very high degree up to $13,989.83 \pm 595.46$ % and this is attributed to the combination of acrylic acid and hyaluronic acid which creates a highly absorbant and stable hydrogel.

The diffusion coefficient of the samples was measured using data obtained during swelling analysis and ranged from 3.338×10^{-6} to $4.002 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ as shown in the table in Fig. 6. In the control samples there was a difference in initial diffusion into the hydrogels depending on crosslinker amount, with higher diffusion occurring at lower levels of crosslinker. The 0.16_CON sample had a lower diffusion rate to the other samples, likely due to a high density of crosslinks making the diffusion of PBS more difficult. However, the addition of nanoparticles reduces this disparity between samples with only 0.203×10^{-6} in the difference between samples. Interestingly, in this case the 0.16_NP sample has the highest diffusion of PBS in the hydrogel, much higher than its 0.16_CON counterpart. These results show agreement with the swelling results, in that the addition of nanoparticles presents a way to regulate the swelling and diffusion.

3.4. Thermal characterisation

Fig. 7 shows the thermal decomposition of the hydrogels, with all samples showing similar behaviour. Initial weight loss of 3 % occurred in most samples due to the evaporation of water. For control samples, most of the weight loss occurs between 160°C and 500°C which corresponds to degradation of polymeric side chains and main chains. Following 500°C the sample weight remained relatively constant with a final weight of 11–14 % char [48]. The incorporation of nanoparticles into the hydrogel has minimal influence. For 0.08_CON samples a larger initial weight loss is recorded, and this is related to a higher water content in the sample.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) is an important characteristic of a hydrogel as it gives insight into a material's mechanical characteristics and crosslinking. A material with a low T_g is generally softer and more flexible and usually correlates with a higher crosslinking density.

Fig. 5. SEM images of lyophilised 0.08_NP, 0.12_NP, 0.16_NP and 0.12_NP hydrogels. A- cross-sectional internal porosity of scaffolds. B- magnification of PEDOT:HA nanoparticle clusters on the internal surfaces of the AA/HA/LIG/PEDOT:HA scaffolds.

To avoid a broad endotherm due to moisture loss in the hydrogel, only the second DSC heat scan of the samples thermogram is displayed in Fig. 7(c). Differential scanning calorimetry was carried out on the samples and the glass transition temperatures were all in the range of 120.95–124.63 °C. No melting event is seen in the second heat scan below 200 °C as expected. The increase in crosslinking density and the loading of nanoparticles increased the glass transition temperature of the hydrogels, as shown in Table 2.

3.5. Mechanical testing and adhesion

Mechanical testing was carried out on hydrogel samples using a DMA in compression mode. The hydrogels were subjected to a multi frequency-strain sweep between 0.1 and 10 Hz at room temperature. Generally, across all samples the storage modulus (E') increases with increasing frequency. The storage modulus also increases with an increase in crosslinker amounts due to increased crosslinking occurring in the samples and thus stiffer materials. The loss modulus also increased

Fig. 6. Swelling graphs over 48 h of samples swollen in PBS at 37 °C, $n = 3$. With table insert of diffusion coefficients of samples calculated from swelling results.

Fig. 7. (a) TGA graphs comparing the weight loss up to 700 °C on Samples without nanoparticles, (b) TGA graphs comparing the weight loss up to 700 °C on Samples with 1 % (w/v) nanoparticles, (c) DSC thermograms of hydrogels.

with increasing crosslinker amounts and with increasing frequency. However, it remained lower than the storage moduli in all samples indicating that elastic properties dominate in these hydrogels.

Tensile Testing of the samples was conducted to investigate their mechanical properties. The stress-strain profiles of the 0.08, 0.12 and 0.16 with and without nanoparticle additions are shown in Fig. 8(e). The

Table 2
Tg of all samples as determined from the DSC thermographs.

Sample	Onset glass temperature Tg (°C)
0.08_CON	120.95
0.08_NP	122.65
0.12_CON	122.37
0.12_NP	124.63
0.16_CON	123.22
0.16_NP	123.5

modulus and tensile strength of the hydrogels were determined from Fig. 8(e) and the data obtained is presented in Fig. 8(c-d). The Young's Modulus, as shown in Fig. 8(d), increases with increased crosslinker amounts in the control samples and nanoparticle samples. In this case the 0.08_CON hydrogels show the lowest E overall, with all samples except for the 0.08_NP sample showing a statistical difference. The addition of nanoparticles in the 0.12 and 0.16 samples decrease their

Young's Modulus from 81.33 kPa and 85.34 kPa, to 75.94 kPa and 77.11 kPa respectively. Whereas in the 0.08 samples, nanoparticle addition improves its modulus considerably from 50.34 kPa to 70.07 kPa, significantly improving this samples resistance to deformation. In relation to the tensile strength seen in Fig. 5(c), the addition of nanoparticles reduces this value in the 0.08 and 0.12 samples, whereas in the 0.16 samples the tensile strength increases from 151 to 195 kPa, reducing its risk of breaking under tension. This correlates with previous results discussed earlier in Sections 3.1 and 3.3 in which nanoparticle addition has slowed the crosslinking in these samples and likely caused the hydrogel to become less stiff due to a lower crosslinking degree. Regarding the tensile strength of these materials, the highest performance is seen in the 0.12_CON samples with a high tensile strength of 222 kPa, whereas there is no significant difference between the modulus of any samples except for the 0.08_CON sample which is significantly lower. In polymer synthesis, he increased addition of crosslinker increases the mechanical characteristics of a hydrogel to a point, but after

Fig. 8. (a-b) DMA graphs of storage (E') and loss (E'') modulus of 0.08_CON, 0.12_CON and 0.16_CON samples, (c) Tensile strength of all samples (**** $p < 0.0001$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD). (d) comparison of the tensile Young's Modulus of all samples and (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD). (e) stress vs strain graph of all samples.

this point the material can become stronger, stiffer and less flexible. In the case of the CON samples the addition of 0.12 % crosslinker would seem to be the optimum for mechanical characteristics, as the tensile strength is reduced in the 0.16_CON sample. Whereas in the NP samples, the highest 0.16 % crosslinker shows the best overall mechanical characteristics. A balance must be struck between crosslinker amount and nanoparticle addition in order to obtain the desired mechanical performance. Note: In Fig. 8(a) only **** $p < 0.0001$ is used, as there was not space for all annotations in the figure.

Sodium lignosulfonate was added to the hydrogels in order to improve adhesion strength of the hydrogels and thus, the adhesion behaviours of the PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels and a control PAA/HA hydrogel were investigated by conducting a 90° peel test on hydrogels adhered to porcine skin. Fig. 9 presents the adhesive strength results, with 9(c) comparing the adhesive strength of PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels with different crosslinker amounts to a PAA/HA hydrogel containing no lignin as a control sample (0.16_CON_NOLIG). All PAA/HA/LIG samples have high adhesion properties, with the 0.08 % and 0.12 % BACA exhibiting a higher adhesion strength at 222 N/m² and 223 N/m² respectively, than the 0.16 % BACA hydrogel with an adhesion strength of 206 N/m². This implies that for adhesive applications, an excessively high level of crosslinking is undesirable. Lignosulfonates were incorporated into the hydrogel in order to improve adhesive strength further and this can be seen in Fig. 9(c) in which the PAA/HA sample containing no lignin has a considerably lower adhesion strength of 86 N/m². The 0.16_CON_NOLIG sample has only 41.7 % of the adhesion strength of the 0.16_CON sample, 38.7 % of the 0.08_CON sample and 38.5 % of the 0.12_CON sample. This is due to an increased hydrogen bonding

capacity in the LIG hydrogels due to the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups in lignosulfonate. One way ANOVA supports these findings, as seen in Fig. 9(c), showing a statistical difference between the NOLIG sample and all samples containing lignin. Fig. 9 (d-f) presents the adhesive characteristics of the hydrogels on (d) glass, (e) metal and (f) plastic. It can be clearly seen that these hydrogels have excellent adhesion to a range of surfaces indicating that these materials have potential for adhesive biomedical applications.

3.6. Biocompatibility testing

An Alamar Blue proliferation assay was used to investigate any possible cytotoxic effects of the AA/HA/Lig/NP materials. NIH-3 T3 fibroblasts were seeded onto the hydrogel materials and fluorescence was used to record their proliferation over 48 h in comparison to a control sample containing just cells seeded on a well plate. The PEDOT:HA nanoparticles have previously been reported as biocompatible [42]. In Fig. 10(a), the proliferation of cells increased in all samples over the 3-day observation, with the 0.12_CON sample yielding the highest value of 92.5 ± 10.3 % at 48 h. Amongst the NP samples, the 0.12_NP sample displayed the highest proliferation at 48 h of 71.3 ± 4.6 %. In general, the addition of NPs to the hydrogels reduced the cell proliferation capacity in all samples, for example the 0.16_CON sample exhibits a cell proliferation rate of 75.25 ± 12.8 % and this reduces to 69.7 ± 11.3 % in the 0.16_NP samples. At 48 h, all samples show lower proliferation than the control with a proliferation rate of 121 ± 42.8 %. These lower proliferation rates may indicate a limitation of the experimental setup. When seeding cells on a hydrogel, it is much more difficult disperse a

Fig. 9. (a) schematic diagram of 90° peeling tests of hydrogels. (b) image of 90° peeling test. (c) adhesion strength of hydrogels: 0.08_CON, 0.12_CON, 0.16_CON and a 0.16_CON_NOLIG sample containing no lignin. (** $p < 0.01$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD). (d-f) Photographs of PAA/HA/LIG hydrogel adhered to glass, metal and plastic.

Fig. 10. (a): 3 day fluorescence (% reduction of alamarBlue reagent) of all samples compared to control containing only cells. (* $p < 0.05$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD) is indicated where a statistical difference is observed, (b) LIVE/DEAD assay-based cell viability quantification, analysed from images in (c) using ImageJ. (* $p < 0.05$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD). (c) LIVE/DEAD staining of NIH-3 T3 cells seeded onto hydrogels of different crosslinker levels for a period of 48 h.

specific number of cells without cells washing away during the process compared to a much easier cell seeding directly onto a well plate. This may explain the lower proliferation rates to the cell control. This theory also correlates to results in Fig. 10(c) in which difficulty in cell adherence can be observed due to lack of adhesion sites, meaning cells may get washed away during experimental preparation. However, the increase in proliferation rates over time indicates positive proliferation of cells when seeded in the presence of these hydrogels. Poor cell adhesion can also be beneficial in some cases such as wound dressings as it can reduce the adhesion between the hydrogel and skin tissue to allow gentle peeling from wounds. Two-way ANOVA was employed to confirm statistical differences between the control and sample groups.

Fig. 10(c) presents a visualisation of fibroblasts cultured on the hydrogel samples over 2 days and this was obtained via LIVE/DEAD staining, with live cells stained in green and dead cells stained with red. High cell viability is seen in all groups as indicated in Fig. 10(b), with the percentage of live cells being higher than 80 % in all samples. The cells seen in the hydrogel samples are mostly spherical and small with little spindle shaped morphology, which indicates that they possess poor cell adhesion capability due to lack of adhesion sites. There are also much fewer cells observed due to limitations in experimental setup and due to the surface of the hydrogel not being flat once swollen, meaning the images obtained only displays cells on one plane of the uneven surface. Despite poor adhesion to the surface of the hydrogels, the hydrogels possess good viability with the 0.08_CON and 0.12_CON groups exhibiting the highest percentage of live cells at 89.7 ± 2.6 % and 86.8 ± 2.5 % respectively. Similarly to cell proliferation results, the addition of NPs

reduces cell viability slightly with the 0.08_NP samples yielding a viability of 81.5 ± 0.6 % for example. One way ANOVA indicated some statistical difference between the samples and the control but not between sample groups.

3.7. Conductivity analysis

To study the conductivity of the hydrogels, dielectric measurements were conducted. The AC conductivity and dielectric permittivity of the samples at 37°C and at 1 Hz are shown in Fig. 11(a). A reduction in conductivity occurs in the 0.12_NP samples at 1.0543×10^{-4} S/cm compared to the 0.08_NP at 2.023×10^{-4} S/cm and 0.16_NP samples at 5.7897×10^{-4} S/cm. Fig. 11(c) shows the difference of conductivity in the 0.12_NP sample when hydrated and when dry. Hydrated samples show considerably higher conductivity and permittivity than dry samples with the conductivity of the hydrated sample exhibiting a value of 1×10^{-4} compared to 1.32×10^{-11} in the dry sample. This increase in conductivity is likely due to ionic contributions in the water and tissues are generally considered to be volume conductors with electrical communication between cells depending on ion flux. Thus, as the hydrated hydrogel portrays both electrical conductivity from the addition of nanoparticles and ionic influences from the high water content, it could have the potential to reduce the disparity at the interface between biological tissue and electroconductive materials [49]. Fig. 11(b) and (d) shows the frequency dependence of the AC conductivity and dielectric permittivity of the samples. The conductivity increases in all samples with increasing frequency and the dielectric permittivity

Fig. 11. (a) Conductivity at 37 °C at 1 Hz of the AA/HA/Lig scaffolds in a hydrated state comparing crosslinking amounts. (b) Frequency dependence of the conductivity and dielectric permittivity at 37 °C for samples, comparing crosslinker amounts. (c) Conductivity at 37 °C at 1 Hz of the AA/HA/Lig scaffolds, comparing the 0.12_NP in hydrated and dry state. (d) Frequency dependence of the conductivity and dielectric permittivity at 37 °C for samples, comparing the 0.12_NP sample in hydrated and dry state.

decreases with increasing frequency.

Glingasorn et al. similarly used the materials of HA, PAA and lignin to form a hydrogel composite for use as a medical adhesive [33]. This work achieved a compression strength of 28 kPa, whereas the current study examined tensile strengths and achieved a value of 222 kPa. A swelling ratio ($W_s - W_d / W_d$) of 1.3 % was achieved and values of the Young's Modulus or the effect of lignin addition on adhesion strength were not reported in [33]. Zhang et al. synthesised a hydrogel based on PAA and N-hydroxysuccinimide with grafted hyaluronic acid (PAA/HA_{NHS}) for wound dressing applications, adjusting the elastic and adhesive properties through variations in synthesis [50]. The study did not investigate conductivity but reported a lower tensile modulus to the current work of 64.74 kPa compared to 85.34 kPa and a similar swelling ratio of 122 % compared to 114 %. A very high peeling force of 0.54 N was also reported compared to a max of 0.223 N achieved in the current study, indicating that grafting HA with NHS is more beneficial to peel strength than the addition of lignin used in this study. Wang et al. incorporated PEDOT:HA nanoparticles into a chitosan and gelatin (CHI/GEL) hydrogel matrix for nerve regeneration scaffolds and achieved an impressive conductivity of 9.48×10^{-3} (S/cm) from a hydrated scaffold containing 10 % PEDOT:HA in the solution [45]. The sample in this study that is most comparable to the current work is the 2 % PEDOT:HA sample achieving 1.76×10^{-5} (S/cm) compared to a conductivity of 5.79×10^{-4} (S/cm) in the current study with 1 % (w/v) of nanoparticles. The swelling ratio values reported in the CHI/GEL matrix is also much lower at 32 % compared to 114 % achieved by the current materials of (PAA/HA/LIG) showing that the current materials demonstrate a more suitable matrix to support PEDOT:HA NPs for conductive and high swelling applications.

4. Conclusions

The current recipe and synthesis methods produce a novel hydrogel with very high swelling, good mechanical properties, elasticity, rapid crosslinking and stable thermal characteristics. The variation of crosslinker amounts had an effect on the swelling characteristics, curing times and mechanical characteristics of the hydrogels but did not greatly

affect its thermal stability or biological activity. The addition of nanoparticles to these hydrogels also effected the curing of the hydrogels, extending the crosslinking times and generally reducing the viscosity of the hydrogels. The nanoparticles had an interesting effect of regulating the swelling and diffusion of PBS into the hydrogels, rendering the difference of crosslinker less influential in swelling ratios. They also slightly reduced mechanical characteristics, but they had no significant effect on biocompatibility or thermal characteristics. It is important to note that this study only investigates one concentration of PEDOT:HA NP addition (1 % w/v) in order to give an overview of the influence of NPs incorporation on AA/HA/LIG hydrogel characteristics whilst inferring electrically conductivity. Future work could involve a study on effect of different NP % loadings on hydrogel properties and crosslinking kinetics. The addition of sodium lignosulfonate had a considerable improvement on the adhesive properties of the samples, increasing the adhesive strength over 100 %. The most consistent hydrogels overall were the 0.12_CON and 0.12_NP samples which had the best repeatability and curing, the addition of nanoparticles to this hydrogel did not have a drastic change to its swelling, diffusion, curing times or thermal characteristics and the mechanical characteristics of both were also very positive. Overall, all samples portray good biocompatibility with increased fluorescence over 3 days and cell viability above 80 % in all samples, very high swelling degree reaching 9714 %, good conductivity, thermal stability up to 200 °C and good mechanical and adhesive properties, achieving a Young's modulus of 85 kPa and an adhesion strength above 200 N/m². A limitation of these materials that was encountered during the study was the lack of adhesion sites in acrylic acid and hyaluronic acid, leading to poor cell adhesion. For this reason, future work on these materials could also involve investigating methods to introduce cell adhesive moieties. Notably, this novel recipe is highly tailorable and in its current form has good potential for use in adhesive sensors, medical adhesives and bioelectrodes. With further work to improve cell attachment and proliferation it could serve as a potential platform for wound healing, tissue engineering and drug delivery.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Caitriona Winters: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marta Carsi:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maria J. Sanchis:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mario Culebras:** Writing – original draft. **Maurice N. Collins:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- M. Snehal and P. Eswara, "Hydrogel Market Size, Share | Industry Analysis & Forecast, 2027." <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/hydrogel-market> (accessed).
- S. Mantha et al., "Smart hydrogels in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine," (in eng), *Materials* (Basel), vol. 12, no. 20, Oct 12 2019, doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12203323>.
- T.R. Ray, et al., Bio-integrated wearable systems: a comprehensive review, *Chem. Rev.* 119 (8) (2019) 5461–5533, 2019/04/24, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.8b00573>.
- Y. Lee, W. J. Song, and J. Y. Sun, "Hydrogel soft robotics," *Materials Today Physics*, vol. 15, p. 100258, 2020/12/01/2020, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtphys.2020.100258>.
- A. Serafin, C. Murphy, M.C. Rubio, M.N. Collins, Printable alginate/gelatin hydrogel reinforced with carbon nanofibers as electrically conductive scaffolds for tissue engineering, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C*, vol. 122 (2021) 111927, 2021/03/01/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2021.111927>.
- E. Chiani, A. Beaucamp, Y. Hamzeh, M. Azadfallah, A.V. Thanusha, M.N. Collins, Synthesis and characterization of gelatin/lignin hydrogels as quick release drug carriers for ribavirin, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 224 (2023) 1196–1205, 2023/01/01/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2022.10.205>.
- T.-C. Ho, et al., Hydrogels: properties and applications in biomedicine, *Molecules* 27 (9) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27092902>.
- D. Yang, Recent Advances in Hydrogels, *Chem. Mater.* 34 (5) (2022) 1987–1989, 2022/03/08, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.2c00188>.
- Q. Chai, Y. Jiao, X. Yu, Hydrogels for biomedical applications: their characteristics and the mechanisms behind them, (in eng), *Gels* 3 (1) (Jan 24 2017), <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels3010006>.
- L.A. Pérez, R. Hernández, J.M. Alonso, R. Pérez-González, V. Sáez-Martínez, Hyaluronic acid hydrogels crosslinked in physiological conditions: synthesis and biomedical applications, *Biomedicines* 9 (9) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines9091113>.
- M.N. Collins, C. Birkinshaw, Hyaluronic acid based scaffolds for tissue engineering—a review, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 92 (2) (2013) 1262–1279, 2013/02/15/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.10.028>.
- A. Serafin, et al., Electroconductive PEDOT nanoparticle integrated scaffolds for spinal cord tissue repair, *Biomater. Res.* 26 (1) (2022) 63, 2022/11/22, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40824-022-00310-5>.
- S. Khunmanee, Y. Jeong, and H. Park, "Crosslinking method of hyaluronic-based hydrogel for biomedical applications," (in eng), *J Tissue Eng.*, vol. 8, p. 2041731417726464, Jan-Dec 2017, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2041731417726464>.
- A. Serafin, M. Culebras, M.N. Collins, Synthesis and evaluation of alginate, gelatin, and hyaluronic acid hybrid hydrogels for tissue engineering applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 233 (2023) 123438, 2023/04/01/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123438>.
- F. Zamboni, et al., Enhanced cell viability in hyaluronic acid coated poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) porous scaffolds within microfluidic channels, *Int. J. Pharm.* 532 (1) (2017) 595–602, 2017/10/30/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2017.09.053>.
- F. Zamboni, et al., On the bacteriostatic activity of hyaluronic acid composite films, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 260 (2021) 117803, 2021/05/15/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.117803>.
- S. Sugiarto, Y. Leow, C.L. Tan, G. Wang, D. Kai, "how far is lignin from being a biomedical material?," (in eng), *Bioact. Mater.* 8 (Feb 2022) 71–94, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2021.06.023>.
- Y. Meng, J. Lu, Y. Cheng, Q. Li, H. Wang, Lignin-based hydrogels: a review of preparation, properties, and application, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 135 (2019) 1006–1019, 2019/08/15/, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.05.198>.
- M. Culebras et al., "Bio-derived carbon nanofibres from lignin as high-performance li-ion anode materials," *ChemSusChem*, doi:10.1002/cssc.201901562 vol. 12, no. 19, pp. 4516–4521, 2019/10/08 2019, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201901562>.
- M. N. Collins et al., "Valorization of lignin in polymer and composite systems for advanced engineering applications – a review," *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, vol. 131, pp. 828–849, 2019/06/15/ 2019, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.03.069>.
- M. Culebras, M. Pishnamazi, G. M. Walker, and M. N. Collins, "Facile tailoring of structures for controlled release of paracetamol from sustainable lignin derived platforms," *Molecules*, vol. 26, no. 6, doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26061593>.
- A. Beaucamp, M. Culebras, and M. N. Collins, "Sustainable mesoporous carbon nanostructures derived from lignin for early detection of glucose," *Green Chemistry*, 10.1039/D1GC02062E vol. 23, no. 15, pp. 5696–5705, 2021, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC02062E>.
- M. Muddasar, M. Mushtaq, A. Beaucamp, T. Kennedy, M. Culebras, and M. N. Collins, "Synthesis of sustainable lignin precursors for hierarchical porous carbons and their efficient performance in energy storage applications," *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.*, 2024/01/23 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c07202>.
- A. Beaucamp, M. Muddasar, M. Culebras, and M. N. Collins, "Sustainable lignin-based carbon fibre reinforced polyamide composites: production, characterisation and life cycle analysis," *Compos. Commun.*, vol. 45, p. 101782, 2024/01/01/ 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coco.2023.101782>.
- A. Beaucamp, M. Muddasar, T. Crawford, M. N. Collins, and M. Culebras, "Sustainable lignin precursors for tailored porous carbon-based supercapacitor electrodes," *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, vol. 221, pp. 1142–1149, 2022/11/30/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2022.09.097>.
- E. Khadem, M. Ghafarzadeh, M. Kharaziha, F. Sun, and X. Zhang, "Lignin derivatives-based hydrogels for biomedical applications," *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, vol. 261, p. 129877, 2024/03/01/ 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.129877>.
- C. Hachimi Alaoui, G. Réthoré, P. Weiss, A. Fatimi, "sustainable biomass lignin-based hydrogels: a review on properties, formulation, and biomedical applications," (in eng), *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24, no. 17 (Aug 30 2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241713493>.
- G. Sennakesavan, M. Mostakhdemin, L. K. Dkhar, A. Seyfoddin, and S. J. Fatihhi, "Acrylic acid/acrylamide based hydrogels and its properties - a review," *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, vol. 180, p. 109308, 2020/10/01/ 2020, doi:10.1016/j.polydegradstab.2020.109308.
- E. J. Cozens, N. Roohpour, and J. E. Gautrot, "Comparative adhesion of chemically and physically crosslinked poly(acrylic acid)-based hydrogels to soft tissues," *Eur. Polym. J.*, vol. 146, p. 110250, 2021/03/05/ 2021, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2020.110250>.
- E. De Giglio, S. Cometa, N. Cioffi, L. Torsi, and L. Sabbatini, "Analytical investigations of poly(acrylic acid) coatings electrodeposited on titanium-based implants: a versatile approach to biocompatibility enhancement," *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, vol. 389, no. 7, pp. 2055–2063, 2007/12/01 2007, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-007-1299-7>.
- Y.-C. Nho, J.-S. Park, and Y.-M. Lim, "Preparation of Poly(acrylic acid) Hydrogel by Radiation Crosslinking and Its Application for Mucoadhesives," *Polymers*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 890–898doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym6030890>.
- C. Fu et al., "Lignin derived hydrogel with highly adhesive for flexible strain sensors," *Polym. Test.*, vol. 107, p. 107486, 2022/03/01/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2022.107486>.
- B. Glingasorn, N. Yongsapanan, A. Pangon, C. Lin, and S. Ummartyotin, "Synthesis of bioinspired based hydrogel composite from hyaluronic acid/polyacrylic acid and lignin as an adhesive for medical technology," *Emerg. Mater.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 275–284, 2024/02/01 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42247-023-00592-y>.
- J. Zhang, Q. Zhang, X. Liu, S. Xia, Y. Gao, and G. Gao, "Flexible and wearable strain sensors based on conductive hydrogels," *J. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 60, no. 18, pp. 2663–2678, 2022/09/15 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/pol.20210935>.
- C. Fu, Y. Ni, L. Chen, F. Huang, Q. Miao, and L. Huang, "Design of asymmetric-adhesion lignin-reinforced hydrogels based on disulfide bond crosslinking for strain sensing application," *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2022/05/18/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2022.05.101>.
- D. Aycan, F. Karaca, A. Koca, and N. Alemdar, "electro-stimulated drug release by methacrylated hyaluronic acid-based conductive hydrogel with enhanced mechanical properties," (in eng), *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, vol. 231, p. 123297, Mar 15 2023, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123297>.
- G. Kougkoulos, M. Golzio, L. Laudebat, Z. Valdez-Nava, and E. Flahaut, "Hydrogels with electrically conductive nanomaterials for biomedical applications," *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2TB02019J> vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 2036–2062, 2023, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/D2TB02019J>.
- A. Escobar et al., "Electroconductive poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) nanoparticle-loaded silk fibroin biocomposite conduits for peripheral nerve

- regeneration," *Adv. Compos. Hybrid Mater.*, vol. 6, no. 3, p. 118, 2023/05/30 2023, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-023-00689-2>.
- [39] A. Serafin, M. Culebras, J. M. Oliveira, J. Koffler, and M. N. Collins, "3D printable electroconductive gelatin-hyaluronic acid materials containing polypyrrole nanoparticles for electroactive tissue engineering," *Adv. Compos. Hybrid Mater.*, vol. 6, no. 3, p. 109, 2023/05/20 2023, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-023-00665-w>.
- [40] S. Paramshetti, et al., Revolutionizing drug delivery and therapeutics: the biomedical applications of conductive polymers and composites-based systems, (in eng), *Pharmaceutics* 15, no. 4, Apr 10 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15041204>.
- [41] D. Liu et al., "Conductive polymer based hydrogels and their application in wearable sensors: a review," *Materials Horizons*, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3MH00056G> vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 2800–2823, 2023, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/D3MH00056G>.
- [42] C. Winters, F. Zamboni, A. Beaucamp, M. Culebras, and M. N. Collins, "synthesis of conductive polymeric nanoparticles with hyaluronic acid based bioactive stabilizers for biomedical applications," *materials today Chemistry*, vol. 25, p. 100969, 2022/09/01/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2022.100969>.
- [43] Y. Hong, Z. Lin, Y. Yang, T. Jiang, J. Shang, and Z. Luo, "Biocompatible Conductive Hydrogels: Applications in the Field of Biomedicine," *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 9, doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23094578>.
- [44] W. Shuping, Neural stem cell proliferation and differentiation in the conductive PEDOT-HA/Cs/gel scaffold for neural tissue engineering, *Biomater. Sci.* 5 (10) (2017) 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7BM00633K>.
- [45] S. Wang, S. Guan, Z. Zhu, W. Li, T. Liu, and X. Ma, "Hyaluronic acid doped-poly (3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)/chitosan/gelatin (PEDOT-HA/Cs/gel) porous conductive scaffold for nerve regeneration," *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C*, vol. 71, pp. 308–316, 2017/02/01/ 2017, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.10.029>.
- [46] G. He et al., "Preparation and properties of quaternary ammonium chitosan-g-poly (acrylic acid-co-acrylamide) superabsorbent hydrogels," *React. Funct. Polym.*, vol. 111, pp. 14–21, 2017/02/01/ 2017, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2016.12.001>.
- [47] D. Das, P. Ghosh, S. Dhara, A. B. Panda, and S. Pal, "Dextrin and poly(acrylic acid)-based biodegradable, non-cytotoxic, chemically cross-linked hydrogel for sustained release of Ornidazole and ciprofloxacin," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 4791–4803, 2015/03/04 2015, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/am508712e>.
- [48] F. Amalina, A. Syukor Abd Razak, S. Krishnan, H. Sulaiman, A. W. Zularisam, and M. Nasrullah, "Advanced techniques in the production of biochar from lignocellulosic biomass and environmental applications," *Clean. Mater.*, vol. 6, p. 100137, 2022/12/01/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2022.100137>.
- [49] Y. Xu et al., "Conductive hydrogels with dynamic reversible networks for biomedical applications," *Adv. Healthc. Mater.*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 2100012, 2021/06/01 2021, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.202100012>.
- [50] X. Zhang et al., "Fabrication of adhesive hydrogels based on poly (acrylic acid) and modified hyaluronic acid," *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.*, vol. 126, p. 105044, 2022/02/01/ 2022, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbm.2021.105044>.